

MANUFACTURING PRINCIPLES FOR FIBER METAL LAMINATES

J. Sinke

Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Technical University of Delft

Kluyverweg 1, 2629 HS Delft, NL

j.sinke@tudelft.nl

SUMMARY

Hybrid materials combine some favorable properties of metallic materials and fiber composites. This is true for both the performance and for the principles of manufacturing. In this paper hybrid laminate features related to metal alloys are discussed, features related to fiber composites, and features related to the composition of hybrid materials.

Key words: Fiber Metal Laminates, GLARE, manufacturing, formability, Lay-up techniques, Tailor Made

INTRODUCTION

With the application of GLARE in the Airbus A-380 hybrid materials like Fiber Metal Laminates have become mature structural materials for highly loaded structures. These laminates, a combination of metal constituents and fiber reinforced polymers, offer new opportunities for the performance of the structure as well as for its manufacturing. In this paper the focus is on manufacturing issues.

Hybrid materials are a rather new type of materials which have been developed in the last 20-30 years [1]. One type, the Fiber Metal Laminates, is developed at the Technical University of Delft, in cooperation with a number of partners. In particular the GLARE material is investigated intensively [2] and has become one of the new materials used on the large Airbus A380 aircraft: two large sections of the fuselage and the leading edges of the horizontal tail planes are made of GLARE.

GLARE is a hybrid material consisting of alternating layers of thin metal sheets and thin composite layers. The metal sheets in GLARE are made of aluminum alloys (Al-2024-T3 or Al-7475-T6) and the composite layers are assembled from two to four UD-prepreg layers (see Figure 1). The number of layers, expressed in the lay-up (like $(x+1)/x$; e.g. 3/2 lay-up) gives the number of metal layers ($n+1$) and the number of composite layers (n). The composite layers are oriented in one direction, resulting in UD-laminates, or in two directions, resulting in cross-ply laminates. The used resin in the prepreg is an epoxy adhesive, which is tuned to the fiber as well as to the metal constituent. Although GLARE has been specifically aimed at applications of the fuselage, changing the constituents in the FML-concept could result in a large number of different FML-variants. In the past a number of different materials have been investigated like thermoplastic matrix materials, titanium alloys as metal constituents and Aramid and Zylon fibers instead of the glass fibers in GLARE.

Figure 1. Exploded view of a FML (GLARE) with a 3/2 lay-up.

Since metals and fiber reinforced polymers have characteristic properties and features with respect to manufacturing, the manufacturing of hybrid materials has properties and features related to both material groups. With metals it has in common that the hybrid materials to some extent can be deformed plastically. The similarity with the fiber reinforced polymers is processes like the lay-up process, which result in integral and multiple layer components or substructures. This multilayer composition of the hybrid laminates also offer the opportunity to mix and combine constituent materials with the aim to optimize the component or substructure. Such components could be referred to as Tailor Made.

In this paper several manufacturing related topics are discussed, based on research of the last years. First the formability of the laminates is discussed. The metal constituent in the FML offers some plasticity that can be used in forming processes. Secondly, the layered structure of the laminates is essential when the lay-up techniques, applicable on FML, are described. The last two sections are dedicated to the exploitation of the hybrid nature of the FML and new prospects with respect to manufacturing techniques.

FORMABILITY OF FML

Hybrid materials can be plastically deformed permanently into single or double curved shapes. Just like metal alloys, the laminates show plastic behavior. The amount of plasticity depends on the metal alloy. A laminate made of a more ductile alloy like Al-2024 can be deformed more easy than a laminate made of less ductile Al-7475.

However, the plastic behavior is limited to the metal constituents, the fibers don't deform plastically. Therefore, the imposed plastic deformation in fiber direction is limited by the failure strain of the fibers, for glass fibers about 4 to 4.5%. When straining in fiber direction occurs, the elastic stresses in the laminate are significant and will result in a rather high spring back and/or internal stresses. Perpendicular to the fiber direction however, the plastic deformation is dominated by the failure strain of the metal alloys or the adhesive. In transverse direction the in-plane failure strain is 6-8% – a limit set by the adhesive - or higher in case of bending. The limitation of plastic forming by the fiber direction is relevant for cross-ply laminates and in the fiber direction of UD

laminates. Due to the limited formability the forming methods are used for selected structural elements only.

One of the selected items that can be made by forming is the profile or stringer. This element is prismatic and has several parallel bend lines (see Figure 2). When these bend lines are parallel to the (only) fiber direction of the (UD) laminate, so when the deformation is perpendicular to the fibers, than a small bend radius can be achieved. In this way, simple profiles/stringers of 2/1 and 3/2 lay-up laminates can be made without difficulty. Both the minimum bend radius and spring back are almost similar to the values of the constituent metal alloy with the same thickness.

Figure 2. Some stringer geometries made from GLARE in 3/2-lay-up.

However, thicker laminates (4/3-lay-up and larger), are more difficult to bend: for those laminates the minimum bend radius increases nearly exponentially with the lay-up or thickness. Since the shear in the metal/composite interfaces is proportional with the distance to the neutral axis, the shear stresses (stresses in the adhesive) increase likewise. For GLARE laminates with a lay-up like 5/4 and higher, delamination will occur just outside the bend zone (see Figure 3). This location can be explained by the fact that the internal stress system should become zero in the straight flanges.

Bending of cross-ply laminates is only feasible for a 2/1 lay-up where the fibers are in the neutral axis of the bend. However, for stringers the most appropriate material choice is a UD laminate, since the stringer is loaded in length direction anyhow.

Double curvatures are much more complicated shapes. Only shallow double curvatures like stiffening beads are feasible. For any double curvature strains in two orthogonal directions are required, at least one strain in a fiber direction, which is limited. There is one exception: the application of stretching in the so-called bias directions ($\pm 45^\circ$) of the laminate. In this situation the fibers may shear (Trellis effect) and it has been demonstrated that in-plane strains of about 6-7% were achieved.

A typical deep drawing deformation is not feasible since the thin layers tend to buckle.

Figure 3. Shear stresses outside the bend zone in a 3/2 laminate.

LAY-UP TECHNIQUES FOR FML

Fiber Metal Laminates are layered structures, assembled from thin metal layers and thin composite layers. As stated before, each composite layer consists of 2 to 4 prepreg layers. The fiber orientation can be different: 0, +/-45, or 90°. These layered materials are made by lay-up techniques which are typical for composites. After the lay-up of all layers on a preshaped mould, the stack is vacuum bagged and cured in an autoclave at elevated temperature and increased pressure. The temperature and pressures for the GLARE laminates are 120° C and 6-11 bar respectively.

Before lay-up the prepreg is retrieved from rolls, which are 0.5-0.6m wide. The prepreps are precut before lay-up and during lay-up the backup foils are removed. The metal sheets are retrieved from a coil, machined to the right dimensions and pre-treated, by degreasing – pickling- anodizing and the application of a primer, in order to obtain a good bonding surface.

Although the width of the prepreg is limited, by placing the prepreps next to each other (butt type joint) the resin will flow during the cure cycle and result in one homogeneous composite layer. For the metal layers this is different. The width of the metal sheets is also limited; currently the maximum width is about 1.5m. In order to have a proper joint in the metal layers, butt type joints are not an option: this would require very high manufacturing tolerances. For the metal layers the overlap splice joints have been developed (see Figure 4), which have acceptable tolerances and minimum consequences for the local thickness; i.e. the thickness step is small so that stringers or frames over the splice don't need joggles. Applying these splices also offer the advantage that the panel size has become independent from the dimensions of the constituent materials but depends on the size of the autoclave only.

Figure 4. *The splice geometry in a GLARE - 3/2 laminate*

The lay-up technology offers also the opportunity to manufacture integrated skin panels: skin panels with local reinforcements. Most aircraft skin panels need local variations in lay-up and thickness. For example: a fuselage panel needs reinforcements in the window belt area, around doors, near locations where significant loads are introduced like wings, tail planes or engines. In those areas the skin thickness and sometime also the fiber orientation needs to be changed. Addition of fibers in other directions is feasible by adding those fibers during lay-up, e.g. extra fiber layers in $\pm 45^\circ$ direction in the fuselage side panels. Increase of the local thickness can be achieved by locally increasing the number of layers. For this purpose there are two methods: the application of internal doublers: adding layers at the inside of the fuselage, or applying interlaminar doublers: adding layers inside the laminate (see Figure 5). For both cases rules have been established to create smooth transitions from one thickness to another. Internal doublers are often used when significant thickness increases are required; interlaminar doublers for more gradual thickness transitions.

Figure 5. *The concept of interlaminar doublers (3/2 laminate becomes 5/4 laminate).*

The application of interlaminar doublers is also used for tapering laminates. If the skin thickness increases or decreases over a (large) distance the thickness is changed by adding or removing layers, so-called “ply drop-off”. This is used in fuselage sections and can be used in wing panels when the thickness decreases from the root to the tip.

The lay-up of the metal sheets has one difficulty: the metal sheets are rigid and not pliable like the prepreg material. For the lay-up of flat and two-dimensional curved skin panels this is not a problem. The thin sheets are very flexible and can be curved in without effort. For three dimensional skin panels however, the metal sheets should have some in-plane straining and have to be forced onto the lay-up surface using pressure. The magnitude of this pressure depends on the curvature of the skin panel. In case of

small curvatures this pressure is limited and the width of the metal sheets can be large. During the curing process limited residual stresses are introduced in the panel. When the curvature increases the pressure needs to be increased and the sheet metal width should be reduced. The reduced width is related to the maximum allowed elastic stresses in the metal sheets. So, if the curvature increases, or when the radii of the panel decreases, the applicable metal sheet or strip width decreases as well. During the production of A380 skin panels, the curvatures of the 3D skins are very small, so the widths of the metal sheets are between 60/70 – 150 cm. See Figure 6 for two examples of fuselage skin panels: one with an obvious double curvature and one with visible local reinforcements.

Figure 6. Two fuselage skin panels: (left) a double curved panel – not the splice lines; (right) a single curved skin panel with local reinforcements.

The lay-up technique is the most appropriate composite technology to manufacture these large FML skin panels. Other techniques based on resin flow or resin injection techniques are not applicable due to the impermeable sheet metal surface. If dry fibers in between metal sheets have to be injected by resin, only the edges offer the area for the injection of the resin and the extraction of air from the laminate.

TAILOR MADE LAMINATES

The range of possible laminate combinations of metal and composite constituents is unlimited, limited only by the imagination of the designer. Thus far however, only a small number of combinations have been used in real applications. Nevertheless, a larger number has been tested on laboratory scale. The limited number of combinations in current structures (mainly Airbus 380) is related to the chosen development strategy. This strategy aimed for a cost-effective introduction of FML, and therefore it was decided to limit the number of variants to be certified. Due to this choice the development was focused and resulted in the successful introduction of GLARE.

The variables in the FML concept that could be changed in order to arrive at new FML are: the constituents themselves as there are the metal alloy, the fiber system, and the resin, the fiber orientations, thicknesses, number of layers and stacking order of the layers.

Although the practical application of other than ARALL and GLARE laminates is rare, in laboratories a number of new combinations have been investigated; some of them will be described briefly.

First it should be mentioned that current GLARE laminates already involve some slight variations with respect to the original ones. In this respect the Single Sided Clad laminates and the laminates composed of metal sheets with (slightly) different sheet metal thickness can be mentioned. The first variation is developed to provide corrosion resistance and surface finish as requested from the customers (airlines). The second variation is also in use and has very small variations in metal layer and due to these small variations, within the range of 0.3 to 0.5mm, the actual and required thickness of the laminates can become more close.

During the last decade a number of other combinations based on different constituents have been investigated like the TiGr laminates, FML based on carbon fibers and aluminum alloys, FML laminates with thermoplastic resin, FML with alternative aluminum alloys and fibers [3]. Only a few combinations will be discussed here.

Fiber Metal Laminates using carbon fibers more or less exclude the use of aluminum alloys. Main reason is the large difference in electric potential between carbon and aluminum. When moisture comes into the system, which is very difficult to prevent in the long life cycle (30 years or more) a severe galvanic corrosion will damage the aluminum sheets. Therefore, despite the attractiveness of this combination, no viable combinations have been developed yet. The combination of titanium and carbon (or graphite) fibers is feasible. In the US Boeing and MIT did intensive research on combinations of titanium alloys and carbon fibers named TiGr (Titanium-Graphite) [4], laminates were aiming for the B787. With respect to GLARE, the titanium-carbon FML offer additional high static strength properties and, depending on the selected resin, improved properties at elevated temperatures.

Several research projects also investigated thermoplastic resin materials as substitute for the thermoset epoxy. Thermoplastic resin needs higher temperatures for curing and thereby introduces higher residual stresses caused by the differences in thermal expansion coefficients of the constituents. In particular aluminum has a rather high CTE. When the thermoplastic resin is used to improve the formability at elevated temperatures, this is only achieved when compressive stresses are avoided, which will introduce wrinkling. In bending operations it could give an advantage [5]

Another variant that tailors the laminate for a specific application is the Central concept [6], developed for wing structures (see Figure 7). This concept is a FML concept in which a number of thin metal layers are replaced by thick layers, and the composite layers are adapted for the transfer of the higher anticipated shear loads.

All the different variations mentioned, are aiming at and tailored for specific applications. For the manufacture of skin panels by lay-up there are no significant difficulties with respect to the processing of all these variants. However, one should realize that the different constituent have different CTEs, which could influence the spring back and machining processes after curing. These effects are further increased when the laminates become more unbalanced (non-symmetrical).

Figure 7. Two variants of the Central concept.

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

Fiber Metal Laminates offer very good properties for structural applications designed for damage tolerance. Besides that, the laminates can be processed rather easy and also the joining and assembly is not too complicated. Future developments should be aimed at the further development of the laminates and structures, and the development the manufacturing processes. Both directions are briefly discussed.

The developments of laminates and structures could be aimed at the development of stiffened FML skin panels and the creation of new laminate variants.

For stiffened FML skin panels both the skin and stringers should be made of FML. This would improve the performance of the skin panels due to the matching of the material stiffness. In the current GLARE skin/aluminum stringer panels, there is a load shift due to inequality the material stiffness, which would be eliminated when both skin and stringers are made of the same material. For test specimen these FML skin panels have been made already (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Stiffened FML skin panel: Skin, stringer, stringer coupling and butt strap are made of GLARE.

The stringers of the stiffened FML panels can be made by bending or roll forming processes. Stringers and profiles can be made of UD laminates, although to a limited thickness. Thick stringers can be assembled from thin profiles (see Figure 9). If a “stackable” profile cross section is selected, all profiles can be produced in one bending set-up. Another feature is that the assembled profiles can be tailored in length direction by adding or removing profiles.

Figure 9. Thick stringer, assembled from 3 profiles (2/1 lay-up).

The development of the laminate combination can be extrapolated from the variations as described in the previous paragraph. Objectives for new variations could be the development of cheap alloys, special purpose laminates, differences between inside/outside of the laminates, different metal alloys, adhesives or fiber systems in one laminate, etc. Generally these new variations do not pose large problems with respect to manufacturing, although when the non-symmetry in the laminate increases, the difficulties will increase too.

The second direction is aimed at the improvement of the manufacturing processes. Like composite manufacturing the FML has several time consuming and costly production phases. These phases are the preparation of the materials (i.p. the surface treatment of the metal sheets), the lay-up of the different layers, and the autoclave process. For these three phases new developments are needed in the future.

For the pretreatment of the surfaces the tendency is to use more environmental friendly processes, although no significant improvement in throughput time or costs is envisaged yet, because the laminates need a high quality and durable bond. The durability of the bonds is achieved only by the rather costly anodizing processes.

The lay-up process however, can be improved by lay-up automation. The automated lay-up for the composite layers is demonstrated already for full composites and the FML can benefit from the developments in that field. For the automatic lay-up of metal sheets, one could opt for reducing the metal sheet width or to work with preformed sheets.

For the curing of the laminates, currently an autoclave process is used. If the autoclave could be eliminated this would give a considerable reduction in the manufacturing costs. In order to eliminate the autoclave the pressure during curing should be reduced. This

requires new adhesives, which have a low viscosity during curing, and for which the application of vacuum is sufficient. If possible a reduction in curing temperature could further contribute to the reduction of manufacturing costs. Reduction of the pressure to 1 bar maximum, also has consequences for the lay-up of 3D panels. In those cases the sheets need to be preformed.

When stiffened skin panels are made of FML, skins and stiffeners, the option of assembling the skin panels using co-curing principles can be employed.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Hybrid materials like Fiber Metal Laminates have material properties that are linked to its constituent metal alloys and composites. This mixed behavior is also true for the manufacturing processes of FML. FML benefit from improvements and developments in both areas.

The main manufacturing processes for FML are forming processes like bending and the lay-up process. The fibers and the layered structure are the limitations for the forming processes, and the rigidity of the metal sheets is the limit for the lay-up technology.

Since the FML is a concept with many opportunities, new developments may result in much more variants of the concept. The trend in this is to more specific or dedicated laminates.

FML can also benefit from the current large scale industrialization of full composites: a number of technologies can be applied to FML too. In addition, progress should be pursued also on FML specific topics like surface treatment of the metal sheets.

REFERENCES

1. Vlot, A., (2001), GLARE, History of the Development of a New Aircraft Material, Kluwer Academic Publishers
2. Vlot, A., Gunnink, J.W. (ed.) (2001), Fiber Metal Laminates, an Introduction, Kluwer Academic Publishers.
3. Hombergsmeier, E., (2006) Development of Advanced Laminates for Aircraft Structures, ICAS 2006, Hamburg, Germany.
4. Burianek, D.A., Spearing, S.M., (2002), Fatigue damage in Titanium-graphite hybrid laminates, *Comp. Sc. and Techn*, 62, pp 607-617.
5. Mosse, L., et.al., (2006), Stamp forming of PP-based FML: the effect of process variables on formability, *J. of Mat. Proc. Techn.*, 172-2, pp 163-168
6. Roebroeks, G.H.J.J., (2007), The development of Central, DTAS 2007.